

Meaning and Origin of Religion from the Reviewed Literature: An Islamic Perspective

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Abstract

The concept of religion has been a subject of debate. It generates many discussions in many academic fora. Various approaches in understanding the concept of religion were used and thus, different ideas and opinions were produced. According to some, religion is nothing rather than just a belief in spiritual beings. Others consider it as a way of life. But, to the anti-religious approach, religion is like a virus or opium of the people. As for the Muslims, Islam is the only religion and all other religions are null and void. This paper discusses the general concept of religion and the perspective of Islam on Muslims' understanding. In achieving this objective, the paper analyzes some established relevant literature and all sources were duly acknowledged.

Keywords: Religion, Meaning, Theories, Islamic Perspective, Natural Inbuilt, Adam's Progeny.

INTRODUCTION

Religion is a fundamental and integral part of the life of mankind. Despite the tussles and hindrances of anti-religious agents to succumb religion as a valueless affair, yet, it remains relevant to the end this world in the affairs of mankind. Hence, the reader will need to know the meaning and origin of this inevitable subject of human affairs. In the following paragraphs therefore, an attempt is made to analyze and assess the meaning of religion from English and Arabic linguistic derivations, its technical connotations as well as its origin with emphasis to the Islamic perspective.

Meaning of Religion

For proper understanding of the meaning of religion, a careful assessment of its literal connotations as well as technical perspectives was made in the following paragraphs.

Etymology of Religion and Meaning

Both English and Arabic derivations of the word 'religion' were assessed as follows:

a. The English Derivation and its Meaning

In the Etymological Dictionary, the word 'ligament' derives from Latin 'ligamentum', which means anything that ties one part to another is closely akin to 'religare' to bind again, 'religio' a binding back or a binding strongly to one's faith or ethic suggested the derivation of the word 'religion'.¹

In her article on the etymology of the word 'religion', Sarah F. Hoyt² gave out some derivations from different scholars of etymology. But, in summary, her article shows that, the term 'religion' is derived from three origins. The first was from the Latin word 'religare' which means 'to bind'. The rare English words 'religate' and 'religation' suggest the origin of religion as having the root *religare*, to bind. For example, if one says "they are not religated within the same

¹ Partridge, Eric *Origins: A Short Etymological Dictionary of Modern English*, London and New York, Routledge Taylor and Francis e-Library, 2006, pp.1778-1779.

²Hoyt, Sarah F. "The Etymology of Religion," *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, Vol. 32, No. 2, 1912.

communion”, that means they are not united; or to say that people with no religating have no binding power.³ This derivation, therefore, seems to explain the power of religion in a particular society.

The second derivation, according to Sarah, was the Cicero’s view that religion was derived also from the Latin word ‘relegere’, meaning ‘to go through or to go all over again in reading, speech or thought’.⁴ It also means ‘conscientiousness, scruple of conscience, scrupulousness’.⁵ The third derivation, has a similar fundamental meaning with the second (relegere), but not the same origin as it was said to have connection with an English word ‘reck’, which means to heed or to have a care for.

b. The Arabic Derivation and Meaning

The equivalent word for religion in the Arabic Language is ‘دين’ (*dal, ya’* and *nun*) which has various connotations from its linguistic derivations. In his book *al Din wa al Wahywa al Islam*, Mustapha Abdurrazzaq related that there are more than twenty linguistic meanings of the word *diin*.⁶ The authors of *Lisan al Arab*,⁷ *Mu’jam al Wasit*⁸ and *Mukhtar al Sihah*⁹ indicate that the word ‘*al diin*’ with *kasrah* vowel sound (p. *al adyaan*), has various literal meanings. These include: *al adah* (custom), *al Jaza’* (retribution / reckoning / reward), *al qahru* (subjugation / overpowering), *al dhillu* (humbleness) and *al Taa’ah* (obedience) from which the meaning of *al diin* (religion with p. *al adyaan*) was derived. Ibn al Manzur further states that Allah’s name *الدينان* – *al Dayyanu*, which means *al Hakamu al Qady* (the Judge, the Arbitrator), *القهار* – *al Qahharu* (the Subduer, to whom people subjected unconditionally for obedience) was derived.

In his book ‘*al Din*’, Daraz expatiates its meaning which can be summarized into three perspectives.

(1) *Al Diin* means ‘الملك والتصرف’ (supreme power and authority to dispose). For example, if one says “دانه دينا” it means “one has overpowered another”, i.e., he can govern, judge, compel, account, administrate and regulate one’s affairs, which is similar to the characteristics of leaders on their subjects. That is why the Almighty Allah is the only Self-governing in the Day of Judgment: ‘مالك يوم الدين’ i.e., Master of the Day of accountability / repayment / judgment / compensation (for whatever was earned of good or evil during life on this earth).¹⁰ The Prophet (ﷺ) also said: *الكيس من دان* *الكي من دان* i.e., a wise man is the one who calls himself to account (means he judged, adjusted and improved it and refrains from doing evil deeds) and does noble deeds to benefit him after death.¹¹

(2) *Al Diin* means ‘الخشوع والطاعة’ (submission and obedience). For example, if one says ‘دان له’ it means one has submitted himself to obey another. In this case, it refers to submission and obedience or worship and devotion to someone. Therefore, if one says ‘الدين لله’, it means ‘the judgment belongs to Allah’ or ‘a total submission and obedience belong to Allah’.

(3) *Al Diin* also means ‘المذهب والطريقة’ (doctrine and way). For instance, if someone says ‘دان بالشريعة’ i.e., one chooses something as his doctrine and way of life; it means he ties upon, accustoms and characterizes with it. Thus, *diin* from this context refers to a doctrinal or ideological system of a person upon which he characterizes himself based on theory and practice.¹²

³Hoyt, Sarah F. “The Etymology of Religion,” pp.126-127.

⁴Hoyt, Sarah F. “The Etymology of Religion,” p.127.

⁵ It has been suggested that, the above indicates the great fact of duty, of conscience, of moral obligation to a natural law of right, and implies not the faintest restriction upon any human faculty other than the natural obligation of right and truth. Abbot, F. E. “The Derivation from Relegere,” in *the Pamphlet Collection of Sir Robert Stout: Vol.37*, Victoria University of Wellington, 2016.

⁶Abdurrazzaq, Mustapha *Al Din wa al Wahywa al Islam*, Mu’assasatuHindawi li al Ta’limwa al Thaqafah, Al Qahirah, 2013, p.21.

⁷IbnManzur, Muhammad Mukram, *Lisan al Arab*, Dar Sadir, Beirut, Vol. 13, p.164.

⁸ Mustapha, Ibrahim & et-al, *al Mu’jam al Wasit*,Maktabah al Shuruq al Dauliyyah, al Qahirah, 4th Edition, 1425A.H/2004C.E.

⁹ Al Razi, Muhammad Abubakar *Mukhtar al Sihah*, Dar al Fikr, Beirut, Lebanon, 2003, p.212.

¹⁰ See Qur’an.1:4 with particular explanation of: Al Muntada Al Islami, *The Qur’an English Meanings and Notes* by Saheeh International, Dar al Qiraat, Riyadh, 2014, p.1.

¹¹ At Tirmidhi, Muhammad IbnEisa, *Sunan at Tirmidhi*, Abu Khaliyl (Trans.), Hafiz Abu Tahir Ali Za’i (Ed.), Hadith No.2459, Vol.4, the chain of the Hadith is a weak as cited by the editor, Maktaba Darussalam, Riyadh, 2007, p.465.

¹² Daraz, Muhammad Abdullahi *Al Din: BahuthunMuhimmah li DirasatiTarikh al Adyan*, Dar al Qalam, Kuwait, 1390A.H/1970C.E, pp.30-31.

A careful assessment of the aforementioned three linguistic connotations of the word ‘diin’ from the Arabic language indicates some relevant agreements from the three connotations. In a situation whereby Mr. A, for example, overpowered and subdued Mr. B, nothing remains for Mr. B except to subjugate himself and obey the commandments of Mr. A. Therefore, his continual adherence to the tenets and regulations of Mr. A will make him to be accustomed and characterized to certain ideological system of life, which might possibly refer to a particular religion. That is the meaning of the three connotations, from overpowering to submission and obedience, then to doctrinal or ideological system of a person i.e., religion.

The Technical Meaning of Religion

After having analyzed both the English and the Arabic linguistic meanings of religion, one needs to look at its technical meaning from the general and Islamic perspectives. The following are some of the definitions of religion from the general point of view:

According to Durkheim, “religion is a unified system of beliefs and practices relative to sacred things, that is to say, things set apart and forbidden – beliefs and practices which unite into one single moral community called a Church.”¹³ Durkheim’s definition shows that the existence of God is not a fundamental religious dimension; instead, he emphasizes on the sacred things. This is because, according to him, all religious beliefs present one common characteristic, which can be classified into two main domains: profane and sacred, in which the former is the opposite of the latter. He, therefore, considers everything as sacred, depending on a religious presentation.¹⁴

Bradley sees religion as “a way in which man seeks meaning in life and hopes to gain help from the unseen or supernatural forces believed to be at work in the universe. This saving will in turn aid him to avoid evil and to secure positive benefits such as health and long life.”¹⁵ However, this definition represents psychological theory as one will see in the subsequent paragraphs.

Robert Crawford, in his book, cited various definitions of religion reflecting the perspectives of anthropologists, sociologists, theologians, philosophers and others.¹⁶ He finally defines religion as “a belief in God, who is the unconditioned ground of all things, and in spiritual beings, resulting in personal experience of salvation or enlightenment, communities, scriptures, rituals, and a way of life.”¹⁷ This means the belief in God or spiritual beings is the central focus from the above definition, unlike that of Durkheim, which does not pay much attention to God. Even though his enclosure with the term ‘spiritual beings’ might not necessarily refer to God or gods, but rather, the sacred things.

According to Fellows, human beings relate to three aspects of their environment: they deal with the physical world as their material environment, they live with other human beings in the social environment; and in religion, they relate to the transcendent or supernatural environment. He, therefore, sees religion as a connection or relationship between humanity and a transcendent world, state, reality, person, or power.¹⁸ In line with the above, Omoregbe says, “religion is essentially a bi-polar phenomenon; that is an encounter between man and a transcendent deity conceived as a personal being, capable of communication with man.”¹⁹

According to Eliade, religion is an autonomous system, meaning that in its origin and functions, it is not the by-product of other system (i.e., economy and society), does not depend on them, and does not generate them.²⁰ This definition somehow portrays the perspective of theological theory of religious studies which claims that man has nature of religious dimension in himself as explained below.

Abdullahi Daraz defines religion as a belief in a supernatural deity, who deserved to be obeyed and worshipped. In other words, and more comprehensively, he says: “Religion refers to a belief in the existence of a supernatural deity or

¹³ Durkheim, Emile “The Elementary Forms of the Religious Life”, in L. William & V. Evon (Eds.), *Reader in Comparative Religion*, 4th Edition, Harper and Row, New York, 1979, p.29.

¹⁴ Durkheim, “The Elementary Forms of the Religious Life”, p.29.

¹⁵ Bradley, David G. *A Guide to the World Religion*, Prentice Hall, U.S.A., 1963, pp.7-8.

¹⁶ Crawford, Robert *What is Religion?* Routledge, London, 2002, pp.1.3.

¹⁷ Crawford, Robert *What is Religion?* p.201.

¹⁸ Fellows, Ward J. *Religions East and West*, Holt Rinehart and Winston, New York, 1979, p.5.

¹⁹ Omoregbe, Joseph *Comparative Religion: Christianity and other World Religions in Dialogue*, Joja Educational Research and Publishers Limited, Lagos, Nigeria, 1999, p.3.

²⁰ Eliade, Mircea; Couliano, Ioan P. and Wiesner, Hillary S. *The Eliade Guide to World Religions*, Harper Collins Publishers, New York, 1991, pp.1-2.

deities, spiritual in nature, who is sensible and wish-able, having full autonomy in managing and controlling all affairs of mankind and the worlds. The belief shall be accompanied with the means of communication to the deity in a manner of hopefulness and fear, humbleness and glorification”.²¹

The above are some of the definitions of religion from different perspectives. However, it is important to know that the disagreements concerning these definitions were resulted from the several theories attempted to define the origin of religion.

Origin of Religion

As we have seen from the above few definitions, everyone has his own perception on religion. Most of the definitions represent a particular theory or approach to the studies of religion; be it anthropological, psychological, sociological and theological among others. The following are brief synopsis about some of these theories.

i. Anthropological Theory

Anthropological theory of religion being influenced by evolutionary theory claims that societies evolved from the lower to the higher. Thus, according to anthropologists, religion is a creation of man and that animism from the importance of the soul in interpreting dreams, hallucinations and others. Thus, according to them, the origin of religion was from ancestor worship, which suggested that religion had originated in propitiation of the soul of the dead.²²

ii. Sociological Theory

Sociological theory refers to the act of studying religious phenomena without diverting from their special science, i.e., studying religions in the very spirit of their fields. Religion, according to this approach, is a creation of the society. It is a societal instrument for controlling people and molding their minds. Thus, religion to them is an instrument of social control. The society exercises such powerful influence on its members that the later personifies its force into a divine entity. Therefore, to them, the idea of God is nothing other than the personified force of the society.²³

iii. Psychological Theory

Psychological approach to the study of religion is another social scientific discipline which argued that religion is normal experience in depth. They are skeptical concerning the perception of the invisible world or of some person or thing which reveals that world. They, therefore, explained all religious experiences in relation to the invisible world as psychological conditions of the mind. For example, Sigmund Freud (an Austrian neurologist and founder of psychoanalysis: 1856-1939), who was one of the anti-religion, considered religion as the continuation into adulthood of a child's attitude towards his father. According to him, God is an imaginary father which the childhood mentality leads man to form. It is a childishness extended into adulthood which has become a kind of neurosis; he therefore calls it “childhood neurosis”.²⁴

iv. Theological Theory

As for the theological theory, Omoregbe puts that a theological theory of religion explains it in terms of human nature itself which, it claims, has a religious dimension. It is this religious dimension in human nature that makes man permanently religious.²⁵ According to this theory, man has within him, an irresistible desire for the infinite, and a desire which renders him restless until it rests in the infinite. It is this restless search for the infinite which expresses itself in various religions.²⁶

The above are some of the examples of various theories concerning the study of religion. Everyone perceived it for his own perspective. That is why Maishanu opines that one has to know the scope and the nature of what he is studying and the best way of reaching at and understanding it, if not, one may end up employing a wrong or irrelevant method in the

²¹Daraz, *Al Din: BahuthunMuhimmah li DirasatiTarikh al Adyan*, p.52.

²²Maishanu, Isa Muhammad *The Comparative Method in the Study of Religion: A Case Study of Al Amiri and Al Biruni and some selected Modern Western Approaches*, Ph.D. Thesis, Department of Aqidah and Comparative Religion, Faculty of Usuludin, International Islamic University, Islamabad, Pakistan, 1420A.H./1999C.E, p.25.

²³Omoregbe, *Comparative Religion: Christianity and Other World Religions in Dialogue*, p.8.

²⁴Freud, Sigmund. *Encyclopaedia Britannica*.*Encyclopaedia Britannica Ultimate Reference Suite*. Chicago: Encyclopaedia Britannica, 2012; Omoregbe, *Comparative Religion: Christianity and Other World Religions in Dialogue*, p.7.

²⁵Omoregbe, *Comparative Religion: Christianity and Other World Religions in Dialogue*, p.11.

²⁶Omoregbe, *Comparative Religion: Christianity and Other World Religions in Dialogue*, p.11. Probably, theological approach to religion is the key driven force towards the idea of unification or amalgamation of world religions into one (وحدة الأديان) to serve the common purpose. This idea is generally in contrast to the teachings of Islam.

study, with the end result being completely wrong.²⁷ Consequently, this study being under the umbrella of Islamic studies, the method was based on Muslim understanding of the concept of religion. Thus, the study examines the Islamic perspective of the concept as presented below.

Meaning of Religion from Islamic Perspective

Religion can be seen, according to Muslim understanding, as a divine law that enables people with good conscience to attain goodness and happiness in this world and the next with their own desire.²⁸ Specifically, the perspective of Muslim scholars on the religion from Islamic perspective mostly refers to Islam as a religion of all the Prophets of Allah; that is to say, all of them practised nothing but Islam with the meaning of total submission and obedience to the will of Allah.

Taking the linguistic meaning of *al Diin* i.e. obedience and submission, Al Shahrastani considered Islam to be a religious tradition of all the Prophets of Allah.²⁹ In his book *al Din wa al Wahywa al Islam*, Mustapha Abdurrazzaq defined religion as a Divine revelation from the Almighty Allah to His Prophets and Messengers, whom He selected among His servants for the guidance of mankind.³⁰ The above definition can be supported with many verses of the Glorious Qur'an, such as:

And We sent not (as Our Messengers) before you (O Muhammad) any but men, whom We sent revelation. So ask *AhlAdhDhikr* (if you know not). With clear signs and Books (We sent the Messengers). And We have also revealed the *Dhikr* to you so that you may clearly explain to men what was revealed to them, and that perhaps they may reflect.³¹

Verily, we have sent the revelation to you as We sent the revelation to Nuh and the Prophets after him; We (also) sent the revelation to Ibrahim, Isma'il, Ishaq, Ya'qub, and *Al Asbat*, (the offspring of the twelve sons of Ya'qub), 'Isa, Ayyub, Yunus, Harun, and Sulayman; and to Dawud We gave the *Zabur*. And Messengers We have mentioned to you before, and Messengers We have not mentioned to you, and to Musa Allah spoke directly. Messengers as bearers of good news and warning, in order that mankind should have no plea against Allah after the (coming of) Messengers; and Allah is Ever All-Powerful, All-Wise.³²

He (Allah) has ordained for you the same religion which He ordained for Nuh, and that which We have revealed to you, and that which We ordained for Ibrahim, Musa and 'Isa saying you should establish religion and make no divisions in it. Intolerable for the idolaters is that to which you call them. Allah chooses for Himself whom He wills, and guides unto Himself who turns to Him in repentance.³³

The above verses indicate that this religion through which Allah revealed His Divine Message to His Prophets and Messengers is one, and it has never been changed by Him. Although, it is the same religion, it has different prescribed law. *Hudud* (punishable offences) and *Ahkam* (prescribed laws) began from the time of the Prophet Adam. The final prescribed law in its complete form, beauty and wisdom, was sealed with the Prophet Muhammad (ﷺ).³⁴ Therefore, all the Prophets and Messengers are brothers and they practiced one and the same religion as indicated in an authentic Hadith by the Prophet (ﷺ) as narrated by Abu Hurairah (R.A.) where Allah's Messenger ﷺ said:

Both in this world and in the Hereafter, I am the nearest of all the people to 'Isa (Jesus) (A.S.), the son of Maryam (Mary). The Prophets are paternal brothers; their mothers are different, but their religion is one (i.e., Islamic Monotheism).³⁵

ShaykhUthmanbnFoduye in his book *UmdatulUlama'* shows that the meaning of religion comprises the three major issues namely *Iman* (faith), *Islam* (submission), and *Ihsan* (goodness) as responded by the Prophet ﷺ to the questions asked by Angel Jibril.³⁶

²⁷Maishanu, *The Comparative Method in the Study of Religion...* p.17.

²⁸ Al Manawi, Muhammad Abdurra'uf *Al TawqifalaMuhimmat al Ta'arif*, DarulFikr, Beirut, Dimashq, 1410A.H, p.168; See also: Al Jurjani, Aliyu Muhammad *Kitab al Ta'rifat*, MaktabatulLubnan, Beirut, New Edithion, 1985.

²⁹ Al Shahrastani, Muhammad Abdulkarim *Al Milalwa al Nihal*, Dar al Fikr, Bairut Lebanon, 2005, pp.29-30.

³⁰Abdurrazzaq, *al Din wa al Wahywa al Islam*, p.25.

³¹ Qur'an.16: 43-44.

³² Qur'an.4: 163-165.

³³ Qur'an.42: 13.

³⁴ Al Shahrastani, *Al Milalwa al Nihal*, p.30.

³⁵ Al Bukhari, Muhammad bnIsmaiel, *Sahih Al Bukhari*, Muhammad Muhsin Khan (Trans.), Darussalam, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, 1997, Vol.4, p.409, Hadith No.3443.

From the above submission, the consideration of Muslim scholars shows that religion is generally known as Islam and it is the only religion in the sight of Allah. The practitioner of this religion is called Muslim, who believed to be reckoned with and rewarded in the Day of Judgment.

Origin of Religion from Islamic Perspective

The origin of religion in Islamic perspective can be seen in the following paragraphs as depicted by Muslim scholars in their writings.

1. Religion is a natural inbuilt of Creator in every human soul

According to Aasi, Qur'an maintains that the Creator imbued man with the knowledge of His being as the only Creator and the Lord to whom alone man stands as servant (*abd*). This awareness has been bestowed upon man in the form of inborn as an *abd* and a 'Muslim' (one who submits to God) and *Hanif* (one who turns away from all that is false and returns to God alone). This is what has been characterized by the Qur'an as *Fitrat Allah* (God's Religion) on which man is Created.³⁷ The Almighty Allah says in the Glorious Qur'an:

So, set your face (i.e. self) towards the religion as a *Hanif* (inclining to truth). (Adhere to) Allah's *Fitrah* with which He has created mankind. No change should there be in Allah's creation, that is the straight religion, but most men know not.³⁸

In an authentic Hadith narrated by Abu Hurairah, the Messenger of Allah was reported to have said:

Every child is born on *Al Fitrah* (Islamic monotheism) and his parents converts him to Judaism or Christianity or Magianism as an animal gives birth to a perfect baby animal. Do you find it mutilated?³⁹

The meaning of '*fitrah*' in the verse and the Hadith according to the majority of scholars refers to Islam. However, Ibn al Qayyim in his book *AhkamAhl al Dhimmah* cited different views of Muslim scholars in relation to the meaning of *al fitrah*. According to some scholars, it means a predestination upon which one was created i.e. whether he will be unhappy by entering hell (شقي) or happy by entering paradise (سعيد). But he shows that majority say it means Islam.⁴⁰

2. The testimony of Adam's progeny

The awareness and knowledge of the One God as the only *Rabb* (Lord, Master, Sustainer and hence the only deity), and then asking the souls of Adam's progeny to bear testimony to this awareness clearly mentioned in the Qur'an. This means the profession and testimony of mankind in its recognition of God as its sole Master worthy of submission, worship, and obedience.⁴¹ The Almighty Allah mentioned in the following verses:

And (remember) when your Lord brought forth from the Children of Adam, from their loins, their seed and made them testify as to themselves (saying): "Am I not your Lord" They said: "Yes! We testify," lest you

should say on the Day of Resurrection: "Verily, we were unaware of this. Or lest you should say: "It was only our fathers aforetime who took others as partners in worship along with Allah, and we were (merely their) descendants after them; will You then destroy us because of the deeds of men who practiced falsehood.⁴²

3. Mankind is one *Ummah*

Qur'an expresses that all mankind at one time practiced a monotheistic religion. However, with the passage of time they differed, the true monotheistic religion of Allah was distorted. Allah then sent His Messengers to guide them.

Mankind was but one community, then they differed (later); and had not it been for a Word that went forth before from your Lord, it would have been settled between them regarding what they differed.⁴³

³⁶ IbnFoduye, ShaykhUsman, "UmdatulUlama' (Basis of Islamic Scholars),"AbdukhaalidAbdulHafeez Ismail Oyoje (Trans.), in Suleiman Musa (Ed.), *Selected Writings of Sheikh Othman bnFodiyo*, Vol.1, Iqra' Publishing House, Gusau, 2013, p.239.

³⁷ Aasi, GhulamHaiderMuslim *Understanding of other Religions: A Study of IbnHazm'sKitab al Fisal al Milalwa al Ahwa' wa al Nihal*, IIIT, Islamabad, Pakistan, 1999, p.6.

³⁸ Qur'an.30: 30.

³⁹ Al Bukhari, *Sahih Al Bukhari*, Vol.2, p.253, Hadith No.1358.

⁴⁰ IbnQayyim, Al Jauyyah, Muhammad Abubakar, *AhkamAhl Al Dhimmah*, Yusuf Ahmad Al Bakari&ShakirTaufiq Al Aruri (Eds.), Rumadi li Al Nashr, Saudi Arabiya, 1418 A.H. / 1997 C.E., Vol.3, pp.944-968.

⁴¹ Aasi, *Muslim Understanding of other Religions*, p.6.

⁴² Qur'an.7: 172-173.

⁴³ Qur'an.10: 19.

Mankind was one community and Allah sent Prophets with glad tidings and warnings, and with them He sent down the Scripture in truth to judge between people in matters wherein they differed. And only those to whom (the Scripture) was given differed concerning it, after clear proofs had come unto them, through hatred, one to another. Then Allah by His leave guided those who believed to the truth of that wherein they differed. And Allah guides whom He wills to the straight path.⁴⁴

Also, in an authentic Hadith of *Al Qudusi* narrated by IyadbnHimar Al Mujashi'i, from what the Prophet ﷺ narrated from his Lord, He said:

I have created all My slaves *Hunafâ'* (with the inclination to worship Allah alone), but the devils come to them and turn them away from their religion (true path). They forbid to them that which I have permitted to them, and they tell them to associate others with Me for which I have not sent down any authority. Allah looked at the people of earth and hated them, Arabs and non-Arabs alike, except a remnant of the People of the Book.⁴⁵

The above explanation indicates that mankind was created naturally religious and that Islam (i.e. submission to the will and commandment of Allah) is the nature of their religious tradition. That is why the Almighty Allah's instruction to Prophet Musa and Harun to Pharaoh is "to speak to him in soft words; he might recall" (Qur'an.20: 44). IbnTaymiyyah interpreted that to mean that he might recall the knowledge inherent in his original nature regarding his Lord and His blessings on him.⁴⁶

Conclusion

From the foregoing, the paper argued that religion means different things to different people of different perspectives. From the general review, religion refers to believe in God or gods, sacred things among others. Some people, especially the antireligious, believe religion to have created from the society; i.e., a societal instrument for controlling people and molding their minds.

However, in Islamic perspective, as shown in the paper, religion is a divine law that enables people with good conscience to attain goodness and happiness in this world and the next with their own desire. The paper argued that in Islam religion is not created by society; instead, it is a natural inbuilt of Creator in every human soul to worship only One God. This knowledge or awareness of the One God as the only *Rabb* (Lord, Master, Sustainer and hence the only deity) was believed to have been in the souls of Adam's progeny as appears in the Qur'an.

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⁴⁴ Qur'an.2: 213.

⁴⁵ IbnHajjaj, Muslim AbulHussain, *Sahih Muslim*, Nasiruddin al Khattab (Trans.), Huda Khattab (Ed.), Maktaba Darussalam, Riyadh, 2007, Hadith No.2865, p.257.

⁴⁶Ansari, *IbnTaymiyyah Expounds on Islam*, p.4.

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